

A new method to compute more appropriate off-block times and taxiing paths for airport surface management

Wang Ruixin, Ba Bosheng
CAUC-ENAC Joint Lab for ATM
SIAE, CAUC, Tianjin, China
ruixin.wang@recherche.enac.fr

Jean-Baptiste Gotteland
ENAC Lab
ENAC, Toulouse, France
jean-baptiste.gotteland@enac.fr

Gao Yunqi
Hangzhou International Innovation Institute
Beihang University, Hangzhou, China
yunqi.gao@buaa.edu.cn

Huang Tian, Zhao Yifei
Sino-European Institute of Aviation Engineering
CAUC, Tianjin, China
226040096@cauc.edu.cn, ironmeshff@gmail.com

Abstract—Airports, as critical hubs connecting air and ground transportation, play a key role in managing airspace and ground resources. However, increasing flight volumes and dynamic ground conflicts present significant challenges to accurately predicting taxi times and push-back schedules. These uncertainties make it difficult for existing routing methods to coordinate taxiway usage with runway scheduling. To address this issue, this paper introduces a Reverse Time-Window-based Multi-objective A* algorithm (R-TMOA*), which optimizes taxi routes by routing backward from the runway to the stand. This approach enhances taxi time predictions and improves alignment with DMAN schedules. Through simulations based on recorded operational data from Tianjin Binhai International Airport, R-TMOA* is compared with existing methods, including a basic fixed paths strategy and the classical TMOA* algorithm. Results show that R-TMOA* enables 99% of departures to reach the runway on time, supporting punctual pushback and takeoff operations. It reduces conflicts during taxi by 60% and decreases total taxi time by 4,000 seconds per day, while maintaining computational speed efficiency. The proposed reverse routing method further enhances departure scheduling, optimizes taxiway usage, and improves overall airport operational efficiency.

Keywords—airport operation; dynamic routing; reverse routing; departure management

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background Introduction

As the global air transport demand continues to expand, flight volumes are steadily increasing. In 2023, North American airlines saw a 28.3% increase in annual passenger traffic compared to 2022, according to IATA. Eurocontrol reported approximately 10.2 million flights in Europe, marking a 10% rise from the previous year. In China, airports handled

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4.8528 million departing flights, 38.8% increase from 2022 and 1.69% higher than in 2019 [1]–[3]. This accelerated expansion has intensified operational pressures at major airports worldwide. A critical bottleneck emerges in ground movement coordination, highlighting suboptimal allocation of taxiway and runway resources. U.S. Bureau of Transportation Statistics data reveal that air travelers experience average total delays of 29 minutes per flight, comprising 12 minutes at departure and 17 minutes during taxi operations [4]. European aviation authorities report only 71% of flights achieving scheduled departure times [3], while Chinese airports maintained a 79.92% on-time departure rate with average delays of 20.66 minutes [1]. These operational challenges underscore the urgent need for improved ground traffic management strategies in congested hub airports.

Governments worldwide have proposed various policies to address growing airport operational pressures. For example, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) introduced a proposal to promote Airport Collaborative Decision Making (A-CDM), and the U.S. Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) put forward the Next Generation Air Transportation System, which emphasizes advanced taxiway and runway scheduling strategies [5], [6]. Many major hub airports have also proposed expansion plans to better respond to operational pressure. However, simply improving infrastructure can only partially relieve these pressures. A more important challenge is how to use the expanded resources, such as runways and taxiways, in a more efficient way. Combining airport layout upgrades with new organization-based solutions to boost actual efficiency has become a key research topic.

Airport efficiency is influenced by multiple factors, including en-route operations, arrivals and departures flows, and ground operations [7]. As a key point for balancing airspace capacity, airports must follow airspace constraints. For this, in Europe, the Departure Management (DMAN)

systems must provide a take-off schedule compatible with the runways capacities and the take-off slots assigned by the Network Manager in the case of Air Traffic Flow Management (ATFM)-regulated flights. In such cases, Calculated Take-Off Times (CTOTs) are issued by the Network Management Operation Center (NMOC), with a tolerance window of [-5, +10] minutes. If a flight takes off too early or too late, it affects the coordinated use of airspace and disrupts subsequent flights [8]. However, in China, airports such as Tianjin Binhai International Airport do not operate under a centralized network management system and do not apply CTOTs. Instead, take-off times are managed locally by using Target Take-Off Times (TTOT), which serve a similar purpose in scheduling but are not coordinated at the network level.

B. Literature Review

Taxiway routing is central to managing airport ground operations. It aims to improve taxiing efficiency, reduce conflicts, and optimize the use of taxiway resources. In practice, taxiway routing avoids potential conflicts and balances path length, taxi time, fuel consumption, and conflict risk. At many airports, each stand-to-runway path is fixed in advance. When these paths develop conflict hotspots, controllers can adjust flights routes in real time [9], but this fixed-paths approach often makes some flights taxi longer, lower environmental benefits, increased fuel consumption and carbon emissions [10]. To improve this basic fixed-paths strategy, some research work often predefine a set of different possible paths for each flight from stand to runway or runway to stand [11]. Yang et al. [12] proposed a multi-path standardized taxiing route (MPSTR) generation method oriented toward future autonomous taxiing. Based on a System-Optimal Traffic Assignment (SOTA) model and the k-shortest paths algorithm, the approach provides multiple feasible taxi routes to enhance the flexibility of traditional single-path strategies. Although these methods enable route allocation for all flights simultaneously, their ability to predict taxi conflicts is limited, and they are too static to effectively handle dynamic conflicts that arise during taxiing.

With the gradual adoption of automated and intelligent planning systems—such as Advanced-Surface Movement Guidance and Control Systems (A-SMGCS) and A-CDM dynamic routing is receiving more attention. Airport operations change rapidly, and pilot actions or unexpected events can introduce uncertainty in taxi time. Thus, algorithms that include time windows and real-time adjustments, like QPPTW (Quick Path Planning with Time Windows) [13] and AMOA* (airport multi-objective A*) [14], have been proposed to meet these dynamic needs. However, these approaches rely on idealized network models that are hard to apply to actual airport taxiway networks. Some researchers use learning-based algorithms to solve dynamic routing in complex scenarios, but these are still in early stages, and more work is needed to enhance their maturity [15], [16].

To address this, some studies use graph theory and heuristic optimization. For example, Wang et al. applied a Chance Constrained Programming (CCP) model and sample approximation to handle taxi-time uncertainty and reduce both taxi

time and the number of stops [18]. Other studies combine multi-strategy Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) with Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithms and use a pheromone-blending strategy to improve path-planning accuracy and efficiency [11].

Although dynamic routing can adjust routes in real time during taxi, the actual DMAN systems still do not predict future conflicts. This makes it hard to determine the exact taxi time and the moment when an aircraft must leave its stand. As a result, the aircraft take-off times do not always meet the DMAN predictions. In response to this issue, some researchers have proposed an integer programming-based model that jointly optimizes aircraft pushback times and taxiing trajectories [17]. The model aims to minimize ground delay and fuel consumption by jointly optimizing pushback times and taxi routes. To achieve this, a gate-holding strategy is used to reduce departure congestion and improve airport surface efficiency. However, this strategy is essentially a global control mechanism applied uniformly to all flights, lacking the flexibility for individualized scheduling. It mitigates congestion by delaying the overall pushback time but does not account for flight-specific operational contexts, where some flights might instead require different delay. Moreover, determining an appropriate holding threshold remains a key challenge. Therefore, under increasingly complex and dynamic airport operations, there is a pressing need for adaptive, optimizing only taxiway resources is not enough to meet the needs of coordinated airport ground operations and airspace resources. Looking for new methods that can link taxiway and runway resources more efficiently is still a challenge.

In this context, this paper proposes a new approach to compute the time when a departure should leave its gate and the path that it should follow: the principle is to start from the take-off time and position planned by the DMAN, and to explore the possible paths to reach this point at this time, going backward in time, so that the best route for the aircraft will be found from its take-off position until its gate. In this approach, we will consider the reversed graph of the aircraft possible moves. For this reason, we call it the *reverse dynamic routing* method. This approach takes into account all the potential conflicts of the aircraft and is bound to be aligned with the DMAN take-off schedule. Above all, it should calculate more appropriate off-block times and predict more accurate taxi times. This may provide a new idea for airport traffic optimization and airfield capacity assessments in the future.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 provides a detailed description of the airport departure management and routing problem. Section 3 introduces the model used in this study, along with the data sources from the airport, including data preprocessing. Section 4 explains the principles of the Time-Window-based Multi-objective A* (TMOA*) algorithm and its reversed version (R-TMOA*) and its implementation. Section 5 compares the performance of the different routing algorithms within the simulation model. The final section evaluates the effectiveness of the algorithm when integrated with the DMAN system.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

This section explains the coordinated ground taxi operations problem: it focuses on the overall taxi process and how DMAN (Departure Management) and AMAN (Arrival Management) couple with SMAN (Surface Management).

When an arrival is approaching, the AMAN sends the **Target Landing Time (TLDT)** to SMAN, which then plans the taxi path for the arriving flight, based on current taxiways usage and overall conditions. For a departure, as shown in Figure 1, the SMAN system provides the schedule through four stages:

- **EOBT (Estimated Off-Block Time)**, the time that the operator estimates that the aircraft will be ready to start up and leave the stand.
- **ETOT (Estimated Take-Off Time)**, taking into account EOBT plus the estimated taxi-out time.
- **TTOT (Target Take-Off Time)**, the potentially delayed take-off time, taking into account the runway capacity and the ETOT of the next departures.
- **TOBT (Target Off-Block Time)**, deduced from the TTOT and the estimated taxi-out time.

In these stages, the estimated taxi-out time covers the route from the stand to the runway entry. DMAN updates TOBT and TSAT (Target Start-Up Approval Time). It needs to estimate the taxi-out time from SMAN and to calculate TTOT, then it uses TTOT to work out TOBT. This adjusts TOBT and also accounts for runway queuing.

Figure 1: Flowchart of Airport Ground Taxiing Procedures

A. Limitations of Classical routing in Taxi Time Prediction

Currently, airports face two main uncertainties in routing and take-off sequencing that lead to delays and runway queues. DMAN is responsible for determining TTOT and TOBT, but TOBT depends on the estimated taxi-out time, which is subject to prediction errors. Taxi times vary due to factors such as conflicts with other flights occupying taxiways, speed uncertainties, and other operational conditions. This causes discrepancies between estimated and actual taxi time, potentially leading to flights missing their planned runway slots.

Even with dynamic routing to avoid conflicts, unpredicted real-time conflicts in ground operations can still alter significantly the schedule, as illustrated in Figure 2. In this simple example, we assume that the SMAN provides the estimated taxi-out time for flight D as 5 minutes, which means that its push-back time (TOBT) will be $TTOT - 5$ minutes. At this time ($t = 0$ in the figure), D begins its push-back as required,

but then has a conflict with an arrival A entering the stands area. D has to wait one minute, its taxi-out time exceeds the estimation by one minute and it will finally reach the take-off point one minute later than the TTOT.

In this example, even in classical routing, one could think that it would be better to delay (or reroute) the arrival rather than the departure, but the arrival has landed on the runway more than 15 minutes ago, it is already late and, above all, it is also an incoming departure scheduled in the system, so that this solution would be worse. This example highlights that flights starting at different times encounter different conflicts and require more appropriate TOBT. This leads to a paradox: classical routing methods cannot predict taxi-out time with sufficient accuracy, which means flights may not reach the runway on time, potentially causing more taxi delays and runway queues than expected. These inherent limitations of the classical routing methods underscore the need for alternative methods in taxi time prediction.

B. Reverse Routing Method for taxi-out time estimation

In order to improve the taxi-out time estimation and to meet the target take-off times, we propose to start from the take-off position and time of each departure and to compute its route by going backward in time, in order to determine its reversed route until its departure from the stand. This proposed reverse routing method calculates the taxi-out time more precisely, as illustrated in Figure 3. Taking flight D as an example, its start time is TTOT ($t = 5$ in the figure). In each step of the reverse search, the algorithm explores where the aircraft can come from to reach the current position at the current time. When the conflict with the arrival A is detected near the stands area, the conflict resolution time of one minute is deduced, so that the predicted taxi time integrates this needed advance of one minute ahead of aircraft A to reach the TTOT. Ultimately, by simulating taxiing in reverse, we find a total taxi time of 6 minutes, meaning the aircraft should leave the stand one minute before its initially computed TOBT. One can notice that in this case, D is one minute ahead of schedule and could take-off earlier than its TOBT, but this is only if there is no other departure before it: in busy periods, the most important thing is not to be late.

In this reverse routing method, the runway is the starting point, and the stand is the endpoint for departures, with the system searching backward in time. For this, we consider the reversed graph of the possible moves of each aircraft: each node is a position of the aircraft at a given time, and the edges describe from where this aircraft can come from to reach this position at this time. During the search, real-time ground information—such as other aircraft positions and motion states—is used to detect and avoid potential conflicts. Once the algorithm completes the backward search and reaches the stand, we obtain a precise taxi time that accounts for all dynamic factors, resulting in more accurate taxi-out time estimations. This method also provides directly the TOBT, which is effectively aligned with the TTOT, after conflicts resolution. This approach should ensure that departing flights reach the runway on time, reducing runway additional delays,

which could significantly enhances airport ground operations efficiency.

Figure 2: Taxi Conflict Resolution by Classical Routing Methods

III. ROUTING METHOD

This study improves upon the time-window-based dynamic routing algorithm, TMOA*, resulting in the Reverse Time-Window-based Multi-objective A* algorithm (R-TMOA*). The modified TMOA* algorithm, based on the traditional A* algorithm, incorporates adjustments to better suit airport network conditions [9]. These adjustments include introducing conflict resolution time-window information and designing separate forward and reverse routing algorithms. The flow chart of the algorithm is shown in Figure 4.

A. Reverse Time-Window-based Multi-objective A* algorithm (R-TMOA*)

In the R-TMOA* algorithm, the priority of each flight during ground taxiing is planned based on the take-off time required by DMAN. The overall process is similar to the basic TMOA* algorithm, as shown in Figure 4.

Initially, the algorithm receives preprocessed network information (N) and flight data ($flights$). The network data includes runway, taxiway path information, stand details, and taxiway weights. It also includes preprocessed cost information for the A* algorithm, the network cost matrix, and time-window data. The flight data ($flights$) contains various aircraft parameters, such as aircraft type, TTOT, target stands, and used runways.

The algorithm then updates the flight information that requires routing and initializes the parameters necessary for the A* algorithm, including the OPEN and CLOSE sets:

Figure 3: Taxi Conflict Resolution with the Reversed Routing Method

OPEN set: This set stores nodes that need to be evaluated. It contains the starting node initially, and as the algorithm progresses, new nodes are added based on their cost, which is the sum of the actual cost to reach the node ($g(n)$) and the estimated cost to the goal ($h(n)$). The node with the lowest total cost $f(n) = g(n) + h(n)$ is selected for exploration.

CLOSE set: This set contains nodes that have been fully evaluated and processed. Once a node is removed from the OPEN set, it is added to the CLOSE set to avoid reprocessing, improving efficiency and preventing cycles.

These sets, along with the start and end points and cost matrices, help the A* algorithm find the optimal path by prioritizing the most promising nodes.

Although the algorithm follows the overall logic of the TMOA* framework, there are differences in its practical application. Specifically, when determining which flight requires routing, the algorithm must decide whether the flight

is departing or arriving, as shown in the right in Figure 4. The left side of the figure illustrates the main steps of the TMOA* algorithm, while the right side shows the main steps of the R-TMOA* algorithm. The black boxes in both algorithms represent similar steps, while the red boxes in R-TMOA* highlight the differences. If the flight is arriving, the algorithm follows the classical routing process, similar to TMOA*. If the flight is departing, the algorithm selects reverse routing.

• **Reverse Path Expansion**

Upon entering the reverse path expansion phase, the algorithm begins by inputting the current node n , the cost vector G_n for the current node, the path information $path$ that has been expanded, the time window information from the network $timewindow$, and the current time t . A potential solution is selected from the OPEN set for path expansion (as shown in Figure 5, Step 1: Is there a feasible node m preceding n ?). It is important to note that, at this stage, the angle check is reversed compared to classical routing. Unlike in classical routing, where the angle between nodes (s, n) and (n, m) is checked to ensure $\text{angle}[(s, n), (n, m)] < 90^\circ$, here we check whether there exists a node k preceding node m such that the angle between (k, m) and (m, n) satisfies $\text{angle}[(k, m), (m, n)] < 90^\circ$. This ensures that the path from m to n is feasible (as shown in Figure 5, Step 3). Only paths that satisfy this angle constraint are considered valid candidates in the A* algorithm.

The next step involves simulating the changes in aircraft speed during taxi. The R-TMOA* algorithm incorporates the

Figure 5: Reverse Path Expansion

Figure 4: TMOA* Algorithm (On left) & R-TMOA* Algorithm (On right)

cost matrix and precomputed costs for various taxiing speeds to generate an independent cost matrix for each taxiway. Variations in taxi speed directly impact both taxi time and fuel consumption, thus influencing the total cost of the path. Each vector $C_{m,n,p}$ in $C_{m,n}$ represents a combination of costs for different taxi speeds, as shown in equation (1). In this matrix, n and m represent nodes, and $C_{n,m}$ is the cost matrix from node n to node m , with dimensions $p \times q$. Here, p denotes the number of available taxiing speed options on the taxiway, and q represents the dimensions of the objectives used in the study (e.g., time, path length, fuel consumption, etc.). In this study, this is modeled as a two-dimensional vector, where the costs consist of taxi time and fuel consumption.

$$C_{n,m} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{n,m,1,1} & c_{n,m,1,2} & \cdots & c_{n,m,1,q} \\ c_{n,m,2,1} & c_{n,m,2,2} & \cdots & c_{n,m,2,q} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{n,m,p,1} & c_{n,m,p,2} & \cdots & c_{n,m,p,q} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Once the taxi time cost $C_{m,n}$ is determined, the path expansion process proceeds to the time window check (as shown in Figure 5, Step 4). The time window records the permissible time intervals for each segment in the network. Suppose the current time window for segment (m,n) is $[t_1, t_2]$, and the aircraft arrives at node n at time t (as shown in the input section of the flow chart). It is important to note that, in reverse path finding, time decreases, and the time window check differs from classical routing. In classical routing, a flight can arrive before the start of the time window t_1 , allowing a waiting strategy, which leads to additional waiting and fuel costs. In contrast, reverse routing requires that $t_1 < t \leq t_2$, and $t - t_1 > \text{edgcost}[t]$. Therefore, only nodes that meet these conditions are allowed for expansion in the reverse process. As a result, only those vectors in $C_{m,n}$ that satisfy the time window constraints will be retained.

Once a feasible speed option is determined, the speed with the lowest cost is selected for path expansion based on the assigned weights (as shown in Figure 5, Step 6). The cost G_m for reaching node m is the minimum value obtained by adding the cost G_n of node n to each vector in $C_{m,n}$ (where each vector is multiplied by the corresponding weight k_i), and selecting the minimum value from these sums. The path and G_m are then updated accordingly. When node expansion is successful, the algorithm performs a cost prioritization check. If the new cost is lower, the path and graph information are updated, and the updated path is output. Through this process, the algorithm dynamically adjusts aircraft taxi paths, ensuring smooth and safe ground operations at the airport.

• Determining route information for current flight

When the route expansion reaches the current flight destination, the algorithm has determined the complete path for that flight, and the route information is used to update the airport network time-window data. This update provides more precise starting data for the next flights routing, ensuring the smooth progression of each flight path. However, the output of the R-TMOA* algorithm differs from classical routing in its calculation of the current flight path. The algorithm objective is to ensure that the flight reaches the runway take-off point

on time (as described in Section 2) and calculates the taxi-out time based on the reverse routing results, thus determining the push-back time (TOBT). The reverse routing output includes not only the taxi time for each segment but also the specific start time for taxiing (TOBT).

• Update Time Window

A key challenge in implementing this algorithm is updating the time-window information. Both forward and reverse path time windows within the same network must be considered simultaneously. Additionally, the update of time windows is crucial for detecting conflicts for subsequent flights, the process of updating the time windows is shown in Figure 6.

The process begins by inputting the determined path information, the initial taxi time T , and the network time window data. It is important to note that the time T here is different from the input time t in the previous flow chart. In this case, T refers to the actual time the aircraft begins taxi during operations. For arriving flights, this time is the Actual Landing Time (ALDT), and for departing flights, it is the Target Off-Block Time (TOBT). The TOBT is determined by the previous step in the R-TMOA* process (as shown in Figure 4: Determine the path information for the current flight). It is calculated based on the predicted taxi time.

The algorithm then traverses each taxiway segment in the path (denoted as (n,m)), detecting the intersection between the taxiway and the time window information for (n,m) in the network, and removes the time occupied by the aircraft from the network time window.

Since taxiways can be two-ways, different time requirements apply to each direction. For reverse routes calculations, stricter taxi time requirements are applied, and only the final segment of the time window is retained. As shown in Figure 7, the normal time window processing and the improved method

Figure 6: Update Time Window Process

proposed in this study are illustrated. In Figure 7a, under normal time window processing, flight A occupies the taxiway first. However, if flight B arrives at point 4 at $T = 15s$, its time window would allow it to proceed. At $T = 30s$, it would conflict with flight A at point 3, resulting in a severe head-on conflict. In this case, there is actually no conflict in the time window calculation for flight B. To avoid such conflicts, when an aircraft passes, assuming the time window for (n, m) is $[T_1, T_2]$ and the taxi time is $[t_1, t_2]$, the updated time window becomes $[T_1, t_1]$ and $[t_2, T_2]$. For the reverse direction (m, n) , only the remaining time window $[t_2, T_2]$ is kept. As shown in Figure 7b, flight B will only enter point 4 after $T > 40s$, avoiding severe conflicts.

To reduce the computational load, when processing a departing flight, the algorithm removes any time windows that end before the current time t . This means that the algorithm discards time windows that are no longer relevant or possible for the flight's path. After updating the time window data, the algorithm outputs the revised time windows, which will be used for routing subsequent flights. These updated time windows help ensure that future flights are scheduled in a way that avoids conflicts, taking into account the changes made during the current flight's path calculation.

During this process, the reverse calculation of the route helps determine the aircraft push-back time from the stand, ensuring that the flight can reach the take-off point on time and without additional conflicts, as required by DMAN. Ultimately, the R-TMOA* algorithm outputs the flight path with integrated time information.

(a) Issues with the standard time window updating method

(b) Proposed time window updating method

Figure 7: Two different time window updating methods

B. Key advantages of the algorithm

- Integration of Two Different Time Schemes

The core challenge of the reverse routing algorithm lies in how to integrate the results from both forward and reverse pathfinding. Since the two planning processes operate in opposite time directions, calculating them independently makes it difficult to simultaneously account for conflicts between forward and reverse flights. This study addresses this by calculating the forward and reverse paths separately and then merging the path information into a unified network. This approach ensures better alignment with the DMAN target take-off times, improving the overall accuracy of scheduling.

- Maintaining Excellent Algorithm Complexity

Although reverse routing requires reserving feasible taxi time before the unknown take-off or landing times, thereby expanding the management range of time windows, practical analysis shows that the complexity of the reverse TMOA* algorithm remains on the same order of magnitude as the forward TMOA* algorithm, both being $O(n)$. This indicates that while the algorithm enhances compatibility with time requirements, it does not introduce additional computational burdens.

Both forward and reverse methods handle speed variations through the cost matrix and resolve conflicts using the network time windows. However, reverse routing cannot directly adopt the forward approach in terms of direction and time handling, and its conflict detection method differs. Specifically, reverse routing starts from the runway take-off time, treating the take-off point as the path starting point. Classical routing mainly focuses on whether the time window of the forward path satisfies the current taxiing requirements; if it doesn't, the aircraft can wait at the previous node or take an alternate route. In contrast, reverse routing cannot resolve conflicts by waiting.

As shown in Figure 8c, when the aircraft must reach the previous node at a specific time (e.g., Time = 4), there is no path segment available in a given TTOT and time window, this path becomes invalid and must be recalculated. Consequently, as shown in Figure 8d, the aircraft must change the taxiing route or adjust the start time to bypass the conflict. Although this process is more sensitive to time window and path changes, multiple simulation results indicate that the algorithm still maintains high computational efficiency, providing a more flexible dynamic planning option for ground taxiing scheduling.

IV. SIMULATION SETUP

All experimental data in this study are recorded from Tianjin Binhai International Airport. The airport graph was built from the Autocad data (2021 version), provided by Tianjin airport controllers team. The resulting airport graph has been validated by extensive taxiing paths search between all gates and runways. We used realistic, detailed modeling to recreate actual ground operations, and the airport taxiway network is shown in Figure 9. This dataset includes 147 stands, 1,638 taxiways portions, and 2 runways. When building the model, we not only incorporated real airport data but also distinguished various taxiway types. For example, whether a taxiway is one-way or two-way can be a factor. One-way taxiways are mainly used for push-back operations of

(a) Rerouting Strategy in Classical routing

(b) Waiting Strategy in Classical routing

(c) Path Selection Failure in Reverse Routing Due to Conflict

(d) Successful Path Selection in Reverse Routing

Figure 8: Comparison of Conflict Handling Methods between Reverse and Classical routing

departing aircraft and for incoming flights entering stands. The push-back procedure varies with the choice of taxi direction. We also considered how taxiway attributes, such as turning rate, affect the speed of the aircraft. Generally, on a straight taxiway, aircraft taxi at speeds between 3 m/s and 10 m/s. Below 3 m/s, an aircraft is considered to be in an idle taxi state. On turning taxiways, the upper speed limit depends on the turning radius and follows relevant formulas. Because taxi speed is a range rather than a fixed value, we also examined the relation between speed intervals and fuel consumption.

Figure 9: Network Model of Tianjin Binhai International Airport

Using ICAO data on fuel consumption for the CFM56 engine at various taxi speeds, we performed linear fits for idle, 3 m/s, 5 m/s, and 10 m/s speeds to establish the relationship between taxi speed and fuel consumption. The specific relationship is provided in the Table I .

TABLE I. Relationship between Taxiing Speed and Fuel Consumption Rate

Speed (m/s)	Fuel Consumption Rate (kg/s)
10	0.124
9	0.1116
8	0.0992
7	0.0868
6	0.0744
5	0.062
4	0.0496
3	0.0355
0	0.0355

This study employs a model that imposes several restrictions on the selection of aircraft taxi routes. Multiple aircraft are not allowed to simultaneously enter or occupy the same taxiway portion. Aircraft are also prohibited from linking two portions if the angle between them is greater than 90 degrees, and a minimum safety distance of 60 meters must be maintained between aircraft during taxi. Additionally, head-on conflicts must be avoided all along the path [9].

When a taxi conflict is detected, different deconfliction rules are applied depending on the type of conflict. When two or more flights are about to enter the same taxiway portion, the flight with the higher priority is allowed to enter first, while the lower-priority flight must wait or change of path. A flight priority is determined by the order in which its path is planned, which is based on the take-off and landing times provided by DMAN and AMAN.

TABLE II. Wake Turbulence Separation Table

Leading Aircraft Type	Heavy	Medium	Light
Heavy	1 min	1 min	1 min
Medium	2 min	1 min	1 min
Light	3 min	2 min	1 min

In this study, flight priority is ranked according to the Target Take-Off Time (TTOT) provided by DMAN and the Target

Landing Time (TLDT) provided by AMAN. Currently, to explore the potential of dynamic taxi routing, we generate routes sequentially for individual aircraft, without considering simultaneous multi-aircraft routing. Additionally, aircraft classification is used to apply wake turbulence separation rules during runway operations. These separations are applied uniformly to both arrivals and departures, representing a simplified model used for planning, as shown in Table II. For example, if the preceding aircraft is classified as Heavy and the following aircraft as Light, the following aircraft must maintain a 3-minute interval from the preceding aircraft.

The flight data used in this study is sourced from the busiest ten days of flight records at Tianjin Binhai International Airport between 2015 and 2019. Considering an expected 50% increase in flight volume over the next five years, the number of flights in this study is expanded to an average of 779 flights per day. Since detailed projections regarding the growth of each wake turbulence category are not available, we apply a homogeneous increase across all categories as a simplifying assumption. The specific data is presented in Table III.

TABLE III. Flight Data and Projected Flight Volume Increase

Date	Actual Flight Number	Increased 50%(2030)
03-08-2017	499	724
06-08-2017	519	768
14-08-2017	527	783
17-08-2017	517	770
19-08-2017	511	761
18-07-2018	535	801
29-07-2018	529	791
29-09-2018	533	801
01-02-2019	539	807
07-08-2019	524	786

V. COMPARISON & RESULTS

This section discusses the comparison of results obtained from four different routing approaches: Fixed paths, CEPO(Coevolutionary Path Optimization), TMOA*, and R-TMOA*. The comparisons are organized into two groups. The first comparison involves basic taxi time estimation rules, comparing TMOA* with fixed paths strategy and CEPO algorithm. This is to demonstrate the effectiveness of the dynamic routing function in TMOA*. The second comparison focuses on precise taxi time estimation, comparing R-TMOA* with TMOA* (which uses multiple iterations to estimate taxi time more accurately). The objective is to demonstrate that R-TMOA* operates dynamically while effectively integrating with the DMAN system. The experiments were conducted in a single-thread Python 3.10.9 environment (16 GB RAM).

A. Taxi Time Estimation Using Basic Approximations

The fixed paths used in this study comes from Tianjin Binhai International Airport routing rules. Before applying these rules, specific adjustments were made to avoid conflicts between arrivals and departures queuing for runway.

According to the experimental results (shown in Table IV), when the fixed paths strategy is applied, an average of 242 flights reach some unsolvable conflicting positions.

TABLE IV. Comparison of Conflict Handling Methods between Fixed and Forward Routing

Approach Type	Fixed Paths	Fixed Paths + Waiting	TMOA*
Solved Flight Number	538 (68.9%)	780 (100%)	780 (100%)

This happens because the fixed paths strategy requires adjustments when too much paths are conflicting at the same time (e.g., when many aircraft have to enter the same taxiway simultaneously). Lower-priority flights cannot follow their assigned paths and should be rerouted. After introducing time windows and waiting strategies, scenarios where simulated with particular waiting instructions, bringing the results closer to real ground operations. With this refinement, the fixed paths strategy can solve the routing for all flights, but it introduces additional waiting time. The average taxi time increases by 356 s, fuel consumption raise to 35.09 kg, and the average waiting time during taxi increases by 30.99 s.

Figure 10: Multi-dimensional Comparison of Fixed Paths Add Waiting and TMOA* in Flight Simulation Experiments

These results show that relying only on waiting strategies performs poorly in terms of taxi time and fuel consumption, and excessive waiting disrupts smooth airport operations. In this context, the advantages of the TMOA* algorithm become particularly evident. The algorithm dynamically adjusts flights paths and simulates more suitable conflicts resolutions. Compared to the fixed paths strategy (as shown in Figure 10), TMOA* reduces the average taxi time by 12.8%, fuel consumption by 9.8%, and average waiting time by approximately 68.9%. This demonstrates that, compared to the fixed paths strategy, TMOA* effectively reduces airport ground taxi time by dynamically adjusting flights paths rather than increasing waiting times.

In addition to comparing the current fixed paths strategy, this study also evaluates the performance of the TMOA* algorithm against the widely used dynamic routing method, CEPO (Coevolutionary Path Optimization). The CEPO algorithm, based on an improved ripple diffusion method, is designed to solve shortest path problems with dynamic obstacles [19]. This study modified the CEPO algorithm to handle aircraft as dynamic obstacles in the airport network.

TABLE V. Computation Speed Comparison

Solution Type \ Approach Type	CEPO	TMOA*
Average Time Required for Solving a Single Flight (in Second)	8	0.02
Average Time Required for Solving the Daily Flight Volume (in Second)	3503.3	10.2

As shown in Table V, the CEPO algorithm, with a complexity of $O(n^2)$, requires approximately 8 s to solve a single flight taxi path, while TMOA* takes only 0.02 s. For a full day worth of taxi path solving, TMOA* is three orders of magnitude faster than CEPO.

TABLE VI. Comparison of Multi-Indicator Solution Performance between CEPO and TMOA*

Date	Saved taxi time (s)	Reduced fuel consumption (Kg)
03-08-2017	432	83.53
06-08-2017	156	31.24
14-08-2017	-158	46.11
17-08-2017	396	40.91
19-08-2017	755	50.66
18-07-2018	538	53.61
29-07-2018	516	42.76
29-09-2018	-183	42.39
01-02-2019	1161	59.22
07-08-2019	460	40.03

Table VI shows the comparison results of the two algorithms in optimizing taxi time. The difference in taxi time between TMOA* and CEPO is under 2%, indicating that TMOA* is nearly optimal for taxi time. Since CEPO is a single-objective optimization algorithm, it primarily seeks the optimal path by exploring a larger solution space and using a waiting strategy, which increases fuel consumption. In contrast, TMOA* dynamically adjusts the taxi path to reduce excessive waiting, achieving simultaneous optimization of taxi time and fuel consumption.

Overall, TMOA* not only outperforms the fixed paths strategy but also achieves taxi time optimization comparable to CEPO, while considering fuel consumption, and offers a more efficient solution for dynamic routing.

B. Precise Estimation of Taxi Time

To assess the accuracy of predicting taxi times, this study first calculates the initial taxi time using the TOBT sequence. Then, by subtracting the taxi time from the TTOT, a new OBT is derived. The updated OBT is then used to recalculate the taxi paths and times for all flights, with multiple iterations to adjust and minimize errors with the TTOT, preventing early or delayed departures. The results of this method are compared with those obtained using the R-TMOA algorithm, as shown in Table VII.

TABLE VII. Integration of TMOA* and R-TMOA* with the DMAN

Solution Type \ Approach Type	TMOA*	R-TMOA*
Additional Runway Delay Per Day (s)	2602.5	0
Number of Adjusted TTOT	372	5.5

Table VIII compares the computation times of TMOA* with multiple iterations and R-TMOA*. TMOA* requires additional time for each iteration to adjust the OBT and precisely match the TTOT. While the solution speed of R-TMOA* is slower, this is due to the increased computation needed to process additional solution data.

TABLE VIII. Computation Speed Comparison

Solution Type \ Approach Type	TMOA*	R-TMOA*
Average Time Required for Solving a Single Flight (s)	0.08	0.12
Average Time Required for Solving the Daily Flight Volume (s)	62.4	93.6
Iteration Times	>2	1

The simulation results for classical routing still show a significant number of flights failing to reach the runway on time, resulting in approximately 2602.5 s of take-off waiting and delay. In contrast, over 99% of flights in reverse routing can reach their destination on time without any waiting or delays. However, due to strict time window requirements, about 5.5 flights per day in the DMAN sequence cannot have their taxi paths accurately solved and need to adjust their take-off times to find a feasible solution. Therefore, relying on classical routing methods cannot solve the problem of combining airport taxiway and runway resources. TMOA requires adjustments to the departure sequencing, which necessitate the integration of multiple algorithms. In comparison, the R-TMOA* algorithm requires only one calculation to effectively integrate both airspace and ground resources.

Figure 11: Multi-dimensional Comparison of TMOA* and R-TMOA* Flight Path Solving Experimental Results

Figure 11 compares the effectiveness of the TMOA* and R-TMOA* algorithms in airport dynamic ground routing. After applying reverse routing, the average daily taxi time per flight decreased from 310 s to 304 s, reducing the taxi time by 6 s per flight. Although the reduction is small, with more than 770 flights per day, the total taxi time decreased by approximately 4,000 s (over one hour). Additionally, the number of conflicts and conflict duration also significantly decreased: compared to classical routing, the average number of daily conflicts dropped from 435 to 73, a reduction of about 80%, and

the conflict duration decreased from 7,519.2 s to 1,035 s, a reduction of approximately 86%. Therefore, the reverse routing method effectively alleviated ground conflicts and significantly improved overall airport operational efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a Reverse Time-Window-based Multi-objective A* (R-TMOA*) algorithm to optimize routing in airport ground operations. The proposed algorithm, by exploring possible departure routes backward in time, from the runway to the stand, enhances taxi time predictions and ensures better alignment with the Departure Management (DMAN) schedule. The results of this study suggest that R-TMOA* outperforms existing routing methods, such as TMOA*, and provides a more efficient solution for dynamic routing in complex airport environments. Furthermore, in the future, R-TMOA* could be integrated into airport systems such as AMAN and DMAN to assist in determining taxiing routes and TOBT, while enabling coordination with air traffic controllers. This integration of R-TMOA* with the airport system is expected to enhance departure scheduling and optimize taxiway usage, leading to better overall airport operational efficiency.

Future research will involve simulating the use of the TOBT and the flight paths generated by the R-TMOA* algorithm within an airport fast time simulation platform performing ground conflicts resolution and adding uncertainties such as variations in taxiing speeds due to pilots behaviors. Each flight is subject to dynamic speed uncertainty during taxiing, which means that the time window during which a flight occupies a segment becomes a dynamic range. The airport surface status will be periodically updated—for example, every five minutes—to re-evaluate ongoing taxi operations. This approach will enable more accurate modeling and resolution of taxiing conflicts. This will allow for more accurate modeling of taxiing conflicts and their resolution. Additionally, data from major hub airports, including Paris Charles de Gaulle Airport and Beijing Capital International Airport, has been obtained. The algorithm will be applied to larger-scale airports to assess its robustness and adaptability in more complex operational environments. Currently, the solution times of the TMOA* method with multiple iterations and R-TMOA* are within the same order of magnitude. However, the number of runways and taxiways at large airports grows significantly, and TMOA* may struggle to achieve the same results even with two iterations, highlighting the advantage of R-TMOA*, which requires only a single computation. Moreover, aircraft push-back times may be delayed due to additional uncertainties such as ground vehicle movements or passenger boarding processes. Future research will focus on modeling these uncertainties and adjusting the algorithm to address these challenges. Additional comparisons with other advanced routing algorithms will also be explored.

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CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

The source code and datasets used in this study are not publicly available due to institutional or data-sharing restrictions, but can be provided upon reasonable request to the corresponding researcher.

REFERENCES

- [1] CAAC, "Statistical Bulletin on the Development of the Civil Aviation Industry in 2023," https://www.caac.gov.cn/XXGK/XXGK/TJSJ/202405/t20240531_224333.html, 2023.
- [2] IATA, "Global Air Travel Demand Continued Its Bounce Back in 2023," <https://www.iata.org/en/pressroom/2024-releases/2024-01-31-02/>, 2024.
- [3] EUROCONTROL, "European Aviation Overview - Archive 2023," <https://www.eurocontrol.int/publication/eurocontrol-european-aviation-overview-archive-2023>, 2023.
- [4] United States Department of Transportation, Bureau of Transportation Statistics, "Airline On-Time Statistics and Delay Causes," https://www.transtats.bts.gov/OT_Delay/OT_DelayCause1.asp, 2023.
- [5] EUROCONTROL, "European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) introduced a proposal to promote A-CDM," <https://www.eurocontrol.int/publication>, 2023.
- [6] Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), "Next Generation Air Transportation System (NextGen)," <https://www.faa.gov/nextgen>, 2023.
- [7] E. Itoh and M. Schultz, "Designing a framework of integrated aircraft departure and surface traffic operation via queuing network models," in *Proceedings of the Fifteenth USA/Europe Air Traffic Management Research and Development Seminar (ATM2023)*, Savannah, GA, USA, 2023, pp. 5-9.
- [8] EUROCONTROL, "Airport CDM Implementation Manual, V.4," March 2012, <https://www.eurocontrol.int/publication/airport-collaborative-decision-making-cdm-implementation-manual>, 2012.
- [9] B. Ba, Y. Yu, R. Wang, et al., "A New Multiobjective A* Algorithm With Time Window Applied to Large Airports," *Journal of Advanced Transportation*, vol. 2024, no. 1, article 7536217, 2024.
- [10] Y. Q. Gao, T. Q. Tang, J. Zhang, et al., "Which aircraft has a better fuel efficiency? A case study in China," *Transportmetrica B: Transport Dynamics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 491-514, 2021.
- [11] W. Deng, L. Zhang, X. Zhou, et al., "Multi-strategy particle swarm and ant colony hybrid optimization for airport taxiway planning problem," *Information Sciences*, vol. 612, pp. 576-593, 2022.
- [12] H. Lee and H. Balakrishnan, "Optimization of airport taxiway operations at Detroit Metropolitan Airport (DTW)," in *Proc. 10th AIAA Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations (ATIO) Conf.*, Fort Worth, TX, USA, Sep. 2010, paper no. 2010-9151.
- [13] S. Ravizza, J. A. D. Atkin, and E. K. Burke, "A more realistic approach for airport ground movement optimisation with stand holding," *Journal of Scheduling*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 507-520, 2014.
- [14] M. Weiszer, E. K. Burke, and J. Chen, "Multi-objective routing and scheduling for airport ground movement," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 119, article 102734, 2020.
- [15] L. Nan, Q. Jiang, X. Zhu, et al., "Prediction of departure aircraft taxi time based on deep learning," *Transactions of Nanjing University of Aeronautics & Astronautics*, vol. 37, no. 2, 2020.
- [16] Z. Xiang, H. Sun, and J. Zhang, "Application of improved Q-learning algorithm in dynamic path planning for aircraft at airports," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 36677-36687, 2023.
- [17] L. Yang, S. Wang, F. Liang, and Z. Zhao, "A holistic approach for optimal pre-planning of multi-path standardized taxiing routes," *Aerospace*, vol. 8, no. 9, article 241, 2021.
- [18] X. Wang, A. E. I. Brownlee, M. Weiszer, et al., "A chance-constrained programming model for airport ground movement optimisation with taxi time uncertainties," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 132, article 103382, 2021.
- [19] X. B. Hu, M. K. Zhang, Q. Zhang, and J. Q. Liao, "Coevolutionary path optimization by ripple-spreading algorithm," *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, vol. 106, pp. 411-432, 2017.